

ANGER MANAGEMENT AND PHYSICAL WELLNESS OF TEACHERS IN GENERAL SANTOS CITY NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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Abstract: Objectives and Scope: The study aimed to determine the extent of anger management and physical wellness of teachers in General Santos City National High School for the School Year 2017-2018 and their relationship between the respondents' extent of anger management and degree of physical wellness. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational analysis method of research employing quantitative approaches which utilizes an adapted questionnaire validated by an expert on the field of Psychology.

Findings: The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' extent of anger management and physical wellness with almost negligible relationship. It also differ significantly between the respondents' extent of anger management and physical wellness.

Conclusion: The extent of anger management of the respondents either in the classroom or in the workplace is of low extent which indicates teachers were able to manage their anger. On the other hand, the degree of physical wellness is of low extent that indicates teachers sometimes practice physical wellness activities. As to show the relationship between the anger management and degree of wellness of teachers There is a significant relationship between the respondents' extent of anger management and degree of physical wellness with almost negligible relationship or inversely proportional relationship which indicates that the extent of anger management is in low extent having minimal relationship with the degree of teachers physical wellness for it is oppositely practiced sometimes.

Recommendation: It is recommended that the proposed program design for the management of anger and development of physical wellness shall be implemented in order for the school to assist the teachers in improving their health and lifestyle practices.

Keywords: Anger management, physical wellness, teachers' health, descriptive-correlational study, quantitative research, emotional regulation, workplace well-being, health and lifestyle practices, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Everyman gets mad at times. The target of our anger might be a visitor, guest, a love one or even subordinates. Many instances that people got angry for some reasons. They usually do that to their assistants or attendants. One of the difficulties of the teachers are they should know how to deal their anger towards to their colleagues and students. This scenario sometimes happened in the school such as faculty or even in the classroom. Some people frequently gets angry at others, or at themselves. Mad people in their earlier life were criticized or abused reacted to other people in the same manner they were treated.

Prolonged or intense anger and frustration contributes to physical conditions such as headaches, digestive problem, high blood pressure and heart disease. Problems dealing with angry feelings may be linked to psychological disorder such as

anxiety or depression. Angry outburst can be a way of trying to cope with unhappiness, or depressed feelings. Chronic anger creates problems getting along with others, and can lead to involvement in physically or emotionally abusive relationships. Having “a short fuse” is often a factor in other problematic behaviors such as “road rage,” accidents, and getting into verbal or physical fights. (Villanova University, 2017)

While some people openly rage, others have difficulty acknowledging their anger and hold their feelings inside as they avoid the issue that angers them. They may express anger in a “passive-aggressive” way that can take the form of baiting others, or frustrating them. People who express anger in a passive-aggressive manner may fear hurting others or being “a bad person” if they openly express negative feelings. However, they usually end up damaging the relationship because other people usually sense their anger on some level and begin to build resentment towards them. People who are unable to acknowledge anger in themselves often feel hurt by others’ hostility, abusive behavior, or withdrawal from them. (Villanova University, 2017)

In Philippine setting, people in the higher position have the tendency to easily get angry. Managers/ administrators always have in contact with their personnel and subordinates. Some of them develop emotional and physical problem which leads into making abrupt decision which creates chaos in the workplace. Personnel have the hard time to express their ideas to the administrators or boss which leads to misunderstanding and miscommunication.

School administrators in the Department of Education encountered this problem in anger behavior. Difficulties in dealing with their client in schools such supervisors, principals down to different level of teaching job in the government. The impression of the subordinates in the staff and teaching personnel varied in the level of anger of their superiors.

In General Santos City, a lot of anger incidence or circumstances met by the employees who are in the lower level position or even in their level of positions. The health status of the General Santos City National High School administrators, teachers and staff may not be the same from the previous years as affected by their emotional status. The researcher finds interest to study or investigate the relationship between Anger Management and Physical Wellness of Teachers in General Santos City National High School: Basis for Physical Wellness Program.

The researcher as Professor of Physical Education, Health and Music would try his best to conduct this study with hope that the data and findings would be realized on how anger management and health status would give impact to teachers of General Santos City National High School.

Theoretical Background

Theories occur to help people explain how and why particular occurrence happen. This study is basically anchored on the different theories of anger Management and physical wellness of teachers.

In the theory of Bushman (2013) entitled: Anger Management: What works and what doesn’t” discussed the effective and ineffective approaches for managing anger. He stressed out that Anger is an emotional response to as real or imagined threat or provocation or can be range in intensity from mild irritation to extreme rage.

Bushman theorized that Anger is not necessary” bad “emotion. Anger makes people feel strong and powerful which can motivate them to stand up for what they believe is right. He also elaborate that even the American Revolution, the civil rights movement, the feminist movement, the gay rights movement, and many other causes probably benefited from anger and the resultant to willingness to act. Anger also can also motivate people to excel in sports and other domains in which it is beneficial to take a competitive stance. However, He said anger can also motivate people to stand up and fight for things that may be trivial or ill advised.

Bushman (2013) angry people seems to act first, and think later. No doubt Thomas Jefferson’s advice “When angry, count ten before you speak; if very angry, an hundred.” To count to 10 or even a hundred before speaking while angry is aimed at giving people time to reflect on the consequences of their actions and possibly avoid impulsive, destructive acts that will be regretted later. For example, angry people often spout off hurtful comment to loved ones later retract. He follow up that all of us becomes angry, and most of us don’t like it. The question is how to get rid of anger, or at least reduce it.

In this study we can use the theory of Catharsis. Catharsis is the Greek word for cleansing and is used in psychology to explain the process of rapidly releasing negative emotions. Catharsis is the process of venting aggression as a way to release or get rid of emotions. Have you ever been so angry that you went outside and yelled or hit a pillow? Psychologist call this method catharsis. You may have heard someone say something was cathartic; meaning it released emotion. For example, if you are angry you might hit something or scream, and that might make you feel better.

Catharsis Theory

The thought behind catharsis theory is that feelings build up and create pressure if not vented, in the same way air builds up in a balloon until it bursts. Releasing emotions decreases the pressure or tension in the person so they have fewer negative emotions and are less aggressive.

According to this theory is that Sigmund Freud was the first one who practice catharsis theory in psychological therapy. The theory states that expressing or getting out one's aggression and anger should reduce the feeling of aggression. The majority of research on catharsis theory hasn't done much to back it up. Venting aggression does not appear to reduce future aggression. In fact, it might actually make a person angrier. Studies have demonstrated that expressing anger created more anger or hostility when compared to groups that were not permitted to express anger. Despite the opposing evidence, many people still do believe aggression reduces frustration and future aggression.

In therapy settings, catharsis is more than just venting anger. Instead, it's a re-experiencing of a traumatic event and expressing the strong emotions that are associated with them. Therapies that emphasize emotions, such as Gestalt therapy, create role-play simulations to facilitate safe expression of emotions.

Theory Based Anger Control Interventions

In this theory, there are three main philosophies subjugated psychological approaches to anger problems over the past several decades, these are ventilation, reduction and management. Potter and Efron (2005). Ventilationists tend to view the core problem in anger as arising from people's tendencies, under group pressure, to suppress and repress their emotions. The treatment goal, then, becomes giving permission to individuals to fully express their feelings, including anger.

Based on this theory on catharsis, the cathartic practice produced in this manner will help clients relieve their stress, drain their anger, and get on their lives.

Classic Gestalt Therapy as cited by (Polster, 1973) which emphasized upon completing unfinished business, exemplifies this approach. Classic Gestalt Therapy emphasized on reduction, reductionist, on the other hand, focus upon people's tendencies to be too strongly emotional rather than too repress in their emotions.

Beck's cognitive behavior therapy (Beck, 1976) fits this model with its emphasis upon recognizing cognitive distortions that subsequently produce excessively powerful emotional states. The assertiveness training with its concept that appropriate anger expressiveness exists in the middle ground between excessive anger (labelled aggression), and efficient amounts of anger (labelled passivity).

His Cognitive behavioral therapy has been widely burst in terms of programs which design to improve angry management or behavior. The emphasis of this program is more on developing treatment design not only for individual clients but for homogenous groups of client with similar presenting problems which emphasized also by many clinicians. Many psychological models make assumptions about the causes of anger and aggression and the type of therapy that should be employed to help individuals control anger. The following is a discussion of these assumptions for the psychological models most related to CBT (Cognitive Behavior Therapy) theory.

Behavior Theory

According to behavioral theory, individuals respond to situations on the basis of their previous learning in similar situations. Individuals react to environmental cues in terms of stimulus-response sequence. Behaviorists do not believe that these behaviors are permanent rather they can be changed through new learning experiences (Thompson & Rudolph, 2000).

Behaviorists believe that anger is learned just as other behaviors are. Individuals learn to respond aggressively to obstacles in the environment because those responses are reinforced (Adam, 1973). Many theorists believe that learning and particularly history of reinforcement /punishment provides the best explanation for why aggressive behavior occurs. This model suggests that environmental cues may lead to aggressive behavior because these cues were present when aggressive acts were displayed.

Regardless of the position whether anger is learned or innate, most theorists agree that environment play a fundamental role in the performance of aggressive behavior. Most behavior theorists suggest that reduction of anger can be achieved through behavior modification programs that utilize techniques such as direct reinforcement, contracting, time-out, response cost, logical consequences, shaping and token economies (Adam, 1973; Feindler, Marriott, & Iwata, 1984).

Cognitive Behavior Theory

Cognitive behavior theory (Beck, 1976) holds that cognitions are a mediating factor between an event and one's response to that event. The pattern of behavior follows a stimulus cognition response sequence, which is less complex than stimulus-response sequence proposed by behavioral theorists. Beck (1976) hypothesized that there were three factors involved in emotions. The first of these is the cognitive triad which describes how the individual negatively views the self, the world, and the future.

The second factor is schema. It describes the underlying assumptions the individual has about life. These assumptions distort the individual's idea of reality, and may lead to the formation of the third factor, cognitive distortions which are misinterpretations an individual holds about the environment. The interplay of these three factors and the level of misinterpretation and distortion lead the individual to hold emotions about particular situations.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to determine the anger management and physical wellness of teachers in General Santos City National High School. Specifically, this would answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of General Santos City National High School in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Sex; and
 - 1.3. Civil status?
2. What is the extent of anger management of teachers from General Santos City National High School in terms of school related activities in the:
 - 2.1. Classroom; and
 - 2.2. Work Place?
3. What is the degree of physical wellness of teachers in General Santos City National High School?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' extent of anger management and degree of physical wellness?
5. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' extent of anger management and physical wellness when they are grouped into Junior high School and Senior High School?
6. Based on the result of the study, what anger management and physical wellness programs can be developed?

Hypotheses

Ho 1: There is no significant relationship between the anger management and physical wellness of teachers in General Santos City National High School.

Ho 2: There is no significant difference between the anger management and physical wellness of teachers from the Junior High School and Senior High School General Santos City National High School.

Significance of the Study

Studying Anger Management and Health Status of Teachers relevant and timely. This is significant to many individuals and entities specially;

Teachers. The study would give enough information regarding anger management and the manner of dealing with anger in order to develop themselves in having good lifestyles.

Administrators. The results of the research can give the administrators an understanding of the need to encourage faculty to engage different program of activities related to physical wellness for a better physical development. This would be their bases in making different programs to avoid aggression inside the school.

Students. This study can inform students that the administration greatly supports the programs of activities on anger management and physical wellness. Likewise the results if implemented can lead to the improvement of curriculum, instruction and management of GSCNHS.

Parents. The parents as the stakeholder of the school would be aware of the program of the school related to wellness program develop by the school, on the other hand, parents now would be confident of sending their children in school.

Researcher. This will make him more interested in conducting the study since he is curious with the results of the study which will give him an idea that can be shared to all teachers in the Division of General Santos City.

Future Researchers. Future teachers and researchers who will be conducting a study on anger management and health status would be able to use this study as bases for their problem development and related literature.

2. METHOD

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive-correlational analysis method of research under the Quantitative method of research to determine the Anger Management and Health Status of Teachers in General Santos City National High School with the end in view to propose an intervention program that enhanced teachers' personality. Quantitative approach was employed to answer all the research questions covered in this study. Furthermore, it also used the documentary analysis on the physical wellness Status of Teachers by analyzing the results of Teachers under the Junior and Senior High School Curriculum.

Research Environment

This study was conducted at the General Santos City National High School which is situated at Rizal Street, Barangay Calumpang, and General Santos City. The city is located at the southern part of the Philippines and is bounded by three municipalities of Sarangani Province (Allabel, Malungon, and Maasim) and two municipalities of South Cotabato (Polomolok and T'Boli).

The city has 26 barangays and it belongs to the first congressional district of South Cotabato and is one of the three chartered cities of Region XII.

The city's economy is primarily agro-industrial and its commercial areas have a continuing growth due to increasing investors in the area.

Calumpang is one of the biggest barangay in the city with the most numbered population. Economically, it contains big industries (fishing, canning, coconut others) and a growing number of commercial businesses.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the faculty of General Santos City National High School. The distribution of their number is shown in the matrix. The number of respondents totals to 237. The researcher administered the questionnaires to 157 Junior High School and 80 Senior High School Teachers. Proportional allocation is used through Stratified Sampling a kind of random sampling technique in which the population is divided into non-overlapping subpopulations called strata.

Matrix 1: The Distribution of the Respondents of the Study

Respondents			No. of Respondents
	GSCNHS	Faculty	
Junior High School	GSCNHS	314	157
Senior High school	GSCNHS	80	80
Total		398	237

Sampling Technique

The researcher used the Stratified Sampling technique. With this sampling technique all the 157 faculty members from the Junior High School and 80 from the Senior High School became the respondents of the study.

Research Instruments

The following instruments were used in the study:

Questionnaire on the Anger Management of Teachers in GSCNHS. This questionnaire is used to elicit information on the respondents' Anger Management conditions. It discusses on the anger status in the workplace and the classroom.

Questionnaire on Physical Wellness of teachers in GSCNHS. This would show the status and physical condition of the respondents' base on the components of physical fitness. It discusses the physical activities, health and fitness as well.

The instruments that were employed in this study were answered by the teacher which had 27 questions and were answerable by the following rating scale: (5) very high extent, (4) high extent, (3) moderate extent, (2) low extent, and (1) very low extent.

Data Gathering Procedures

The following steps were observed in collecting the data needed in this study:

Seeking permission to conduct a study. A letter was sent to the Schools Division Supervisor of General Santos City and to the school Principal of the General Santos City National High School requesting permission to conduct the study. Please see Appendix A Administering questionnaires. The questionnaires were distributed personally by the researcher to the teachers of Junior High School and Senior High School.

Retrieval of the administered questionnaires. It took three weeks to retrieve all the questionnaires from the teachers of both categories.

Collation of Data. After the questionnaires were retrieved the researcher determined the frequency counts as well as the central tendencies of the perceptions of the respondent. This was done through tabulating the data in the computer.

Processing of the data in the computer. In this stage of the study, the researcher sought the assistance of a statistician in the statistical computations.

Analysis and interpretation of the tabulated data. Results of the tabulated data were analyzed and was given interpretation.

Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the data:

To produce consistency and reliability of the test, mean scores and frequency counts was used to determine the health status of the teachers in General Santos City National High School.

Pearson-r Coefficient of Correlation was used in identifying the relationship between respondents' extent of anger management and degree of physical wellness.

T-test was used to determine the significant difference between the respondents' extent of anger management and physical wellness when they were grouped into Junior High School and Senior High School.

To interpret the scores, rating scales with its quantitative descriptions, were used as shown below:

Tool to Determine Anger Management Condition

Adapted from Mary Ann Fosco, MS, LCPC, NCC, CADC

http://www.outlookassociates.com/angermgmt/questionnaire/testing_anger_control.pdf

Scale	Interval Range	Description
5	4.21-5.00	Very high Extent
4	3.41-4.20	High Extent
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Extent
2	1.81-2.60	Low Extent
1	1.00-1.80	Very Low Extent

Definition of Terms

For the purpose of this study, the following terms are defined operationally:

The important terms or key words used in the study were conceptually and operationally defined to link the terms or variables to the level of measurement it will use. Operationally defined terms will facilitate understanding of the readers on the subject being studied.

Anger Management refers to emotional and personality status of teachers in General Santos City National High School.

Classroom is the learning venue where in students learned through different activities and assessment given by the teachers.

Physical Wellness pertains to physical condition and statuses of the faculty in General Santos City National High School.

Workplace refers to workroom or office where in teachers in school work on their daily life routine as a teacher making their school related activities.

3. RESULTS

Table 1.1: The Profile of Teachers in General Santos City National High School.

Age of the Respondents (n=237)

Age Range/Scale	Junior High School Teachers		Senior High School Teachers		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
61 - 65 years old	3	1.91%	0	0.00%	3	1.27%
56 - 60 years old	7	4.46%	3	3.75%	10	4.22%
51 - 55 years old	15	9.55%	4	5.00%	19	8.02%
46 - 50 years old	14	8.92%	3	3.75%	17	7.17%
41 - 45 years old	17	10.83%	17	21.25%	34	14.35%
35 - 40 years old	30	19.11%	20	25.00%	50	21.10%
31 - 35 years old	31	19.75%	14	17.50%	45	19.00%
26 - 30 years old	26	16.56%	14	17.50%	40	16.88%
20 - 25 years old	14	8.92%	5	6.25%	19	8.02%
TOTAL	157	100.00%	80	100.00%	237	100.00%

The table presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age from both category (Junior High School and Senior High School). It revealed that most of the teachers in the Junior High School were in the middle age in the range of 31 to 35 years old with a percentage of 19.75; followed by the age ranges of 35 to 40 years old with a percentage of 19.11; 26 to 30 years old with a percentage of 16.56; 41 to 45 years old with a percentage of 10.83; 51 to 55 years old with a percentage of 9.55; 26 to 25 years old and 46 to 50 years old with the same percentage of 8.92; 56 to 60 years old with the percentage of 4.46 and 56 to 60 years old with the least percentage of 1.91.

In the Senior High School, the data shows that most of the teachers are in the middle age in the range of 35 to 40 years old with the percentage of 25.00; followed by the age ranges of 41 to 45 years old with the percentage of 21.25; both from 31 to 35 years old and 26 to 30 years old have the same percentage of 17.50; 20 to 25 years old with the percentage of 6.25; 51 to 55 years old with the percentage of 5.00; both from 56 to 60 years old and 46 to 50 years old have the percentage of 3.75; and in the age range of 61 to 65 years old with no respondents.

The overall results shows that most of the respondents are from the middle age range of 35 to 40 with the percentage of 21.10 and the least are from the age range of 61 to 65 years old with the percentage of 1.27

Table 1.2: Sex of the Respondents (n=237)

Sex	Junior High School Teachers		Senior High School Teachers		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	36	22.93%	38	47.50%	74	31.22%
Female	121	77.07%	42	52.50%	163	68.78%
TOTAL	157	100.00%	80	100.00%	237	100.00%

Table 1.2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. In the Junior High School, there is a 121 (77.07%) female teachers and 36 (22.93%) male teachers. In the Senior High School there is 163 (68.78%) female teachers and 74 (31.22%) male teachers.

The total results shows that 163 (68.78%) are female teachers and 74 (31.22%) are male teachers.

Table 1.3: Civil Status of the Respondents (n=237)

Sex	Junior High School Teachers		Senior High School Teachers		TOTAL	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Single	44	28.03%	28	35.00%	72	30.38%
Married	108	68.79%	52	65.00%	160	67.51%
Widowed	5	3.18%	0	0.00%	5	2.11%
TOTAL	157	100.00%	80	100.00%	237	100.00%

Table 1.3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of civil status. The Junior High School shows that there are 108 (68.79%) married, 44 (28.03%) single and 5 (3.18%) widowed teachers. In the Senior High School, there are 52 (65.00%) married, 28 (35.00%) single and 0 (0.00%) widowed teachers. The total results shows that 160 (67.51%) are married teachers and 72 (31.22%) are single teachers and 5 (2.11) are widowed teachers.

I. The Extent of Anger Management of the Respondents

Table 2.1: Extent of Anger Management of the Respondents in the Classroom (n=237)

Statement	Junior High School Teachers		Senior High School Teachers		TOTAL	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. It's hard for me to let go of thoughts that make me angry.	2.03	Low Extent	1.96	Low Extent	1.99	Low Extent
2. I feel depressed, guilty or anxious when I experience anger in the classroom.	2.27	Low Extent	2.33	Low Extent	2.30	Low Extent
3. I get angry in the class with little or no provocation.	1.88	Low Extent	1.67	Low Extent	1.77	Low Extent
4. When I become angry, I have urges to beat a learner.	1.73	Low Extent	1.57	Low Extent	1.65	Low Extent
5. When I become angry, I have urges to break or tear things in class.	1.69	Low Extent	1.50	Low Extent	1.59	Low Extent
6. When I am angry, I feel like running away or withdrawing from the classroom.	1.92	Low Extent	1.86	Low Extent	1.89	Low Extent
7. I get impatient when learners don't understand me.	2.03	Low Extent	2.00	Low Extent	2.01	Low Extent
8. My anger becomes too intense when conflict in the class arises.	2.04	Low Extent	2.01	Low Extent	2.03	Low Extent
9. I feel uptight/tense when my learners bully his classmates.	2.17	Low Extent	2.22	Low Extent	2.19	Low Extent
10. I yell and/or curse in class.	1.85	Low Extent	2.15	Low Extent	2.00	Low Extent
11. When I am angry I sometimes grit my teeth or get headaches.	1.84	Low Extent	1.55	Low Extent	1.70	Low Extent
12. I get so angry I feel like I am going to explode with rage.	1.87	Low Extent	1.76	Low Extent	1.82	Low Extent
13. I easily get frustrated when things go wrong or do not work properly.	2.04	Low Extent	2.34	Low Extent	2.19	Low Extent
14. I can't tolerate incompetence. It makes me angry.	1.96	Low Extent	2.26	Low Extent	2.11	Low Extent
Overall Mean	1.95	Low Extent	1.94	Low Extent	1.95	Low Extent

The extent of anger management of the teacher-respondents in the classroom has an overall mean of 1.95 which is qualitatively interpreted as low extent. The results for both the Junior and Senior High School are almost the same with a mean of 1.95 and 1.94, respectively which is qualitatively interpreted as low extent. Although in low extent ($\bar{x} = 2.27$), the Junior High School teacher-respondents feel depressed, guilty or anxious when they experience anger in the classroom.

The finding reveals that anger had caused a slight degree of depression, guilt and anxiety among teachers. It is a good sign that even something provokes the teachers, they do not break or tear things in class ($\bar{x} = 1.69$) or beat a learner ($\bar{x} = 1.73$). As reported by the participant during the FGD, that an expression, like “Go out from the sewing machine!” was said to a student. It was a way to express that the teacher was angry (in voice) but deep inside was not. The teacher- respondent applied the *Catharsis Theory*. In the Senior High School, the indicator with the highest mean ($\bar{x} = 2.34$) although qualitatively interpreted as low extent is “I easily get frustrated when things go wrong or do not work properly”. The finding manifests that the teacher-respondents slightly got frustrated when things go wrong or do not work properly. Good thing with the Senior High School teachers is that they did not break or tear things in class ($\bar{x} = 1.50$) and sometimes grit one’s teeth or get headaches ($\bar{x} = 1.55$) when they are frustrated or things do not work properly. A participant shared during the FGD that that he will just count to hold his temper and maintain self-control. The teacher truly applied the *Catharsis Theory*.

The overall results of both the junior and senior high school teachers, showed that they feel depressed, guilty or anxious when they experience anger in the classroom ($\bar{x} = 2.30$) qualitatively interpreted as low extent. The result shows that the high school teachers felt a slight depression, guilt, and anxiety. There are situations in the classroom that trigger their anger like feeling uptight / tense when learners bully his classmates ($\bar{x} = 2.19$) and easily get frustrated when things go wrong or do not work properly with the same mean ($\bar{x} = 2.19$). Although teachers are slightly stressed, however they are able to control it. They had the lowest tendency to beat a learner ($\bar{x} = 1.65$, low extent) or break or tear things in class ($\bar{x} = 1.59$, low extent).

Teachers nowadays are more conscious about the policies and guidelines mandated by the Department of Education Orders that no corporal punishments must be imposed to students.

The almost similar overall mean of the junior high school teachers ($\bar{x} = 1.94$) and senior high school teachers ($\bar{x} = 1.94$) reveals that they are able to manage their anger in the classroom. As McGuire (2003) emphasized that teaching is one of the most rewarding profession. The teachers enthusiastically take care learners and must be able to cope with stress and anxiety that inevitably accompany the teaching task.

Table 2.2: Extent of Anger Management of the Respondents in the Workplace (n=237)

Statement	Junior High School Teachers		Senior High School Teachers		TOTAL	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. I get impatient when my colleagues are bullying me.	1.90	Low Extent	1.99	Low Extent	1.95	Low Extent
2. I embarrass friends, or co-workers with my anger outbursts.	1.71	Low Extent	1.69	Low Extent	1.70	Low Extent
3. When a colleague is inconsiderate, it makes me angry.	1.90	Low Extent	2.06	Low Extent	1.98	Low Extent
4. My anger affects my ability to sleep	1.94	Low Extent	2.03	Low Extent	1.98	Low Extent
5. I often deal with my anger by using alcohol or drugs	1.59	Low Extent	1.35	Very Low Extent	1.47	Very Low Extent
6. Stomachaches are common for me when I am angry	1.67	Low Extent	1.49	Very Low Extent	1.58	Low Extent
7. I have a really bad temper	1.74	Low Extent	1.61	Low Extent	1.68	Low Extent
8. I often wish I had medication to control my anger	1.69	Low Extent	1.46	Very Low Extent	1.58	Low Extent
9. When I am angry I sometimes grit my teeth or get headaches	1.68	Low Extent	1.48	Very Low Extent	1.58	Low Extent
10. I yell or scream at a co-employee when I become angry	1.64	Low Extent	1.58	Low Extent	1.61	Low Extent
11. I get so angry I feel like I am going to explode with rage.	1.68	Low Extent	1.56	Low Extent	1.62	Low Extent
12. I get easily frustrated when things go wrong or do not work properly.	1.90	Low Extent	2.16	Low Extent	2.03	Low Extent
13. I remember people and situations that make me angry for a long time.	2.31	Low Extent	1.95	Low Extent	2.13	Low Extent
Overall Mean	1.80	Low Extent	1.72	Low Extent	1.76	Low Extent

Table 2.2 presents the extent of anger management of teacher-respondents in the workplace. The overall mean of 1.76 which is qualitatively interpreted as low extent reveals that the teacher-respondents are able to manage their anger in the workplace. The overall mean of the Junior High School ($\bar{x} = 1.80$) and the Senior High School ($\bar{x} = 1.72$) shows a slight difference on their ability to manage anger. The data show that the senior high school teachers are able to manage their anger compared to the junior high school teachers as shown in the mean difference.

The Junior High School teachers remember people and situations that make them angry for a long time ($\bar{x} = 2.31$). The data manifest that the junior high school teachers has a slight tendency to hold grudges to people or situations that made them angry. While the Senior High School teachers easily get frustrated when things go wrong or do not work properly ($\bar{x} = 2.16$). The data reveals that the SHS teachers had the slight tendency to be frustrated easily when things do not happen as planned. In the FGD with the teachers, a participant mentioned that to handle anger, she “*accepts the reality sets up priority*”. Another participant mentioned that teachers are slightly stressed because the school lacked socialization activities. Others burst their anger on social media like Facebook. As Morris, Denham, Bassett and Curby (2013) found in their research that teachers’ use of socialization techniques did contribute to the prediction of the preschoolers’ scores.

Although there are people or situations that slightly pushed high school teachers to be angry in the workplace but they did not use alcohol or drugs ($\bar{x} = 1.35$, very low extent) to escape from their anger. Hairston (2018) emphasized that controlling and limiting anger is important in every aspect of one’s life. Anger if not managed well can limit what one can actually accomplish.

II. The Degree of Physical Wellness of the Respondents

Table 3: Degree of Physical Wellness of the Respondents (n=237)

Statement	Junior High School Teachers		Senior High School Teachers		TOTAL		Interpretation
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	
1. I exercise aerobically (vigorous, continuous) for 20 to 30 minutes at least three times per week.	0.88	Sometimes	0.89	Sometimes	0.88	Sometimes	Physically Fit
2. I do exercises designed to strengthen my muscles and joints.	1.03	Sometimes	1.06	Sometimes	1.05	Sometimes	Physically Fit
3. I have lots of energy and can get through the day without being overly tired.	1.18	Sometimes	1.31	Sometimes	1.25	Sometimes	Physically Fit
4. I do some stretching exercises everyday	1.11	Sometimes	1.15	Sometimes	1.13	Sometimes	Physically Fit
5. I get 7-8 hours of sleep each night.	1.17	Sometimes	1.19	Sometimes	1.18	Sometimes	Physically Fit
6. I avoid drinking alcoholic beverages or I consume no more than one drink per day	1.17	Sometimes	1.26	Sometimes	1.21	Sometimes	Physically Fit
7. I engage in recreational activities	1.18	Sometimes	1.21	Sometimes	1.20	Sometimes	Physically Fit
8. My body heals itself quickly when I get sick or injured	1.19	Sometimes	1.21	Sometimes	1.20	Sometimes	Physically Fit
9. I maintain a regular schedule of immunizations, physicals, dental checkups and self-exams	0.96	Sometimes	0.93	Sometimes	0.94	Sometimes	Physically Fit
10. I maintain a reasonable weight, avoiding extremes of overweight and underweight.	1.15	Sometimes	1.24	Sometimes	1.20	Sometimes	Physically Fit
Overall Mean	1.10	Sometimes	1.15	Sometimes	1.12	Sometimes	Physically Fit

The Junior High School teachers had the highest mean of 1.19 in the indicator of “My body heals itself quickly when I get sick or injured”. The finding reveals that the JHS teachers are physically healthy as shown in the ability of their body to naturally heal from sickness. However, the JHS teachers need to exercise aerobically (vigorous, continuous) for 20 to 30

minutes at least three times per week ($\bar{x} = 0.88$). Even though the teachers are slightly performing vigorous exercise but their body heals quickly when sick. There could be other activities that made them physically fit. The Senior High School teachers have lots of energy and can get through the day without being overly tired ($\bar{x} = 1.31$). The data reveal that SHS teachers are energetic. Similar to the JHS teachers, they sometimes exercise aerobically (vigorous, continuous) for 20 to 30 minutes at least three times per week ($\bar{x} = 0.89$). The data mean that there could be other physical activities that they do that keep their energy.

It indicates that teachers were not really doing this things and there is a need for the teachers to be in a good condition all the time since the students in the classroom lies on them every day. And even as a challenged for the teachers to be in good shape with high level of endurance they should go in work out and exercise every day even simple exercises that will circulates the blood to avoid us from fatigue and stress.

III. The Significant Relationship between Respondents’ Extent of Anger Management and Degree of Physical Wellness

Table 4: Relationship between Respondents’ Extent of Anger Management and Degree of Physical Wellness (n=237)

Items Correlated	\bar{x}	Computed r_{xy}	Description	t-Computed	p-value	Remark
Extent of Anger Management	1.86	- 0.02	Almost Negligible Relationship	15.70	0.00	Significant
Degree of Physical Wellness	1.12					

It can be gleaned on Table 4, that the computed p value is 0.00 which is lesser in the level of significance of 0.05. The computed r value is -0.02 described as almost negligible relationship with the computed t value of 15.70. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between respondents’ extent of anger management and degree of physical wellness. As described, it has inversely proportional relationship with its significant result and almost negligible relationship. The results signify that when the teachers are able to manage their anger, they will become healthy physically. On the other hand, people who are not physically healthy tends to be more anxious, stressful, and easily gets angry.

The Wellness Reproductions, Inc. (1991) emphasized that when a person is able to manage anger he will increase daily energy level; develop effective communication skills; strengthen relationship; improve physical and mental health; and boost self-esteem.

. The significant Difference between the Respondents’ extent of anger management and physical wellness when they are grouped into Junior High School and Senior High School

Table 5: Significant Difference Bet ween the Respondents’ Extent of Anger Management and Physical Wellness when Grouped into Junior High School and Senior High School (n=237)

Variables	Junior High School Teachers		Senior High School Teachers		t- value	p-value	Remarks
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Extent of Anger Management	1.88	0.69	1.83	0.54	0.54	0.59	Not Significant
Physical Wellness	1.10	0.33	1.15	0.35	-0.92	0.37	Not Significant

Not significant $\alpha = 0.05$

It can be gleaned on Table 5 that the Extent of Anger Management has the p value of 0.59 which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05 and with the computed t -value of 0.54. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the respondents’ extent of anger management and physical wellness. The Physical Wellness has the p -value of 0.37 which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05 and with the computed t -value of -0.92. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the respondents’ extent of anger management and physical wellness they are grouped into Junior High School and Senior High School. The result implied that both the JHS and SHS teachers’ ability to manage anger could either affect their physical wellness or vice versa.

Schutt (2013) mentioned that exercise gives people an opportunity to channel their emotions especially when they feel that they cannot take the situation anymore. The best theory centers on serotonin levels in the brain. It is a chemical known to be responsible for regulating the behavior of the brain which can be very helpful for people who have great tendencies towards aggression. Similar to the findings of the present study, that if both the teachers in the JHS and SHS will be given equal chances to participate in activities that will help them manage their anger, the healthier they will become physically.

The study identifies areas for enhancement for both JHS and SHS teachers on how to manage their anger and maintain physical wellness. Following the model of the Department of Education in designing enhancement programs, the researcher proposed wellness program based on the findings of the study.

4. DISCUSSION

Findings

The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' extent of anger management and physical wellness with almost negligible relationship. It also differ significantly between the respondents' extent of anger management and physical wellness.

Conclusion

The extent of anger management of the respondents either in the classroom or in the workplace is of low extent which indicates teachers were able to manage their anger. On the other hand, the degree of physical wellness is of low extent that indicates teachers sometimes practice physical wellness activities. As to show the relationship between the anger management and degree of wellness of teachers There is a significant relationship between the respondents' extent of anger management and degree of physical wellness with almost negligible relationship or inversely proportional relationship which indicates that the extent of anger management is in low extent having minimal relationship with the degree of teachers physical wellness for it is oppositely practiced sometimes.

Recommendation

It is recommended that the proposed program design for the management of anger and development of physical wellness shall be implemented in order for the school to assist the teachers in improving their health and lifestyle practices performance.

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